

Enhanced Entrance Examination System of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University Using Java and MySQL

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Abstract

The current entrance examination system of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. combines paper-and-pen and machine. Test papers are printed and answer sheets are checked using an optical scanner. Although this system is effective and efficient, if enhanced more, the benefits of information and communications technology may be enjoyed better. This study focused on the enhancement of the entrance examination system and evaluates its quality. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions: 1) what are the characteristics of the produced software as to functionality, usability, and efficiency?; and 2) what is the evaluation of the personnel in-charge and students on the quality of the produced software as to functionality, usability, and efficiency? This study employed Scrum methodology and evaluation. The produced software was developed using Java packaged in NetBeans 7.3 and MySQL packaged in XAMPP 1.8.2. The personnel in-charge found the software “very good” while the students found it “good”.

Keywords

system development, entrance exam, Java, MySQL, ISO 9126

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrance examination is an admission requirement in any bachelor’s degree at John

B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo). This aims to gauge the preparation of an entrant to tertiary education. The entrance examination covers three areas, namely: English, Science, and Mathematics and each area contain 50 items. The passing score per area varies depending on the degree program an examinee would want to pursue.

JBLFMU-Molo’s existing entrance examination system combines paper-and-pen and machine. During the conduct of examination, the examinees are given a printed information sheet. The information sheet requires an examinee to write the following information: official receipt number, date of exam, name, address, previous school, age, course, contact number, and one’s reason for enrolling in JBLFMU. Upon completion of the form, an answer sheet and a test paper are then given. Thirty minutes is allotted for each subject. The examinees have to shade the button that corresponds to their answer. The answer sheet is checked using an optical scanner. Results for those who have taken the exam in the morning are released in the afternoon; while, results for those who have taken the exam in the afternoon are released on the following day.

Each corrected answer sheet only contains the total score of the exam. However, a softcopy which contains the raw score is given to the

personnel in-charge for the computation of the scores per area. The personnel in-charge then processes the data using Microsoft Excel to generate the necessary results and statistics about the exam. Such statistics include the number of passers and non-passers per area according to school attended, sex, and course to pursue.

The above description of the entrance examination system is less efficient like any other manual system. The release of exam results requires a longer time. More time is spent in generating essential exam results and statistics. In addition, it consumes more paper.

One way or another, any existing system has something to be improved. Exploring and enjoying the benefits of information and communications technology improves efficiency. Hence, this study is conducted to enhance the entrance examination system of JBLFMU-Molo.

The researchers trusted the capabilities of Java and MySQL. Java as a programming language is designed to enable development of portable and high-performance applications for the widest range of computing platforms possible (Oracle, n.d.). MySQL is an open source SQL database management system developed, distributed, and supported by Oracle Corporation (Oracle, 2013).

This study was extended by determining the evaluation of the students on the quality of the produced software based on the ISO 9126 model. ISO 9126 is an international standard in evaluating software and is divided into four parts namely: the quality model, external metrics, internal metrics, and quality in use metrics. The ISO 9126-1 software quality model identifies six characteristics namely: functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability. Each characteristic is broken down into a total of 27

sub-characteristics of varying number for each main characteristic (Fahmy, et al., 2012).

Lincke (2007) provides the following definitions of the six characteristics. Functionality refers to '*how well software provides desired functions*'. It is divided into five sub-characteristics: suitability, accurateness, interoperability, functional compliance, and security. Reliability pertains to '*how well software maintains the level of system performance when used under specified conditions*'. It is divided into four sub-characteristics: maturity, fault-tolerance, recoverability, and reliability compliance. Usability covers on '*how well software can be understood, learned, used, and liked*'. It is divided into five sub-characteristics: understandability, learnability, operability, attractiveness, and usability compliance. Efficiency involves '*how well software provides required performance relative to amount of resources used*'. It is divided into three sub-characteristics: time behaviour, resource behaviour, and efficiency compliance. Maintainability means '*how well software can be maintained*'. It is divided into five sub-characteristics: analyzability, changeability, stability, testability, and maintainability compliance. Portability is '*how well software can be ported from one environment to another*'. It is divided into five sub-characteristics: adaptability, installability, co-existence, replaceability, and portability compliance.

Figure 1 below depicts the context diagram of the entrance examination system. There are two types of users: the personnel in-charge and the examinee. On one hand, the personnel in-charge supplies the questions, answer key, and time allocation into the system. In return, the system provides the examination statistics. On the other hand, the examinee supplies his/her personal data and answers. In return, the

system provides him/her the random questions and the exam results.

Figure 1. Context diagram of the system

This study focused on the enhancement of the entrance examination system of JBLFMU-Molo and evaluation of its quality. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions: 1) what are the characteristics of the produced software as to functionality, usability, and efficiency?; and 2) what is the evaluation of the personnel in-charge and students on the quality of the produced software as to functionality, usability, and efficiency?

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized the Scrum software development methodology and evaluation for the descriptive study.

Scrum is founded on empirical process control theory, or empiricism asserting that knowledge comes from experience and making decisions based on what is known. It employs an interactive, incremental approach to optimize predictability and control risk. The heart of Scrum is Sprint. Sprint is a time-box of one month or less during which a “Done”, useable, and potentially releasable product Increment is

created. Sprints consist of Sprint Planning Meeting, Daily Scrums, the development work, the Sprint Review, and the Sprint Retrospective (Schwaber& Sutherland, 2011).

Among the types of descriptive study is evaluation. Evaluation aims to see if a given program is working according to the goals set for it (Best & Kahn, 2003).

2.2 Software Development

In system’s development, the researchers considered number of Sprints that addressed the following major outputs: system model, database design, interface, and working software. Dataflow diagram (DFD) was used to model the system. Entity-relationship diagram (ERD) was used to depict the database design and XAMPP 1.8.2 for Windows was used to manage the database. NetBeans 7.3 was used to develop the interface. Java was the programming language used and MySQL was the database management system used.

Each Sprint was consisted of five events such as: Sprint Planning Meeting, Daily Scrums, the development work, the Sprint Review, and the Sprint Retrospective. The team was consisted of the following: Product Owner, Development Team, and the Scrum Master. The specific tasks and team composition were adapted as explained in the paper of Schwaber and Sutherland (2011), entitled “The Scrum Guide”.

In everySprint Planning Meeting, the team answered the following questions: 1) ‘*What will be delivered in the Increment resulting from the upcoming Sprint?*’; and 2) ‘*How will the work needed to deliver the Increment be achieved?*’.

For the Daily Scrum, each Development Team member, spearheaded by another researcher, explained the following: 1) ‘*What has been*

accomplished since the last meeting?; 2) 'What will be done before the next meeting?; and 3) 'What obstacles are in the way?'

During the Sprint Review, the following tasks took place: 1) One of the researchers acted as the Product Owner who identified *'what has been "Done" and what has not been "Done"'*. 2) The Development Team discussed *'what went well during the Sprint, what problems it ran into, and how those problems were solved'*. In addition, 3) the Development Team demonstrated *'the work that it has "Done"'* and answered the questions about the Increment. 4) The Product Owner discussed *'the Product Backlog as it stands'* and projected likely completion dates based on progress to date. 5) The entire team collaborated *'on what to do next, so that the Sprint Review provides valuable input to subsequent Sprint Planning Meetings'*.

During the Sprint Retrospective, the following tasks were performed: 1) inspected *'how the last Sprint went with regards to people, relationships, process, and tools'*; 2) identified and ordered *'the major items that went well and potential improvements'*; and 3) created *'a plan for implementing improvements to the way the Scrum Team does its work'*.

2.2. Software Evaluation

As a sort of pilot testing, the developed software was installed in one of the computer laboratories of the University. The software for the personnel in-charge was installed in one the computers and the software for the examinees was installed in the other 30 computer units. The three personnel in-charge for entrance examination and 30 students selected through quota sampling were directed to use the software and answer the instrument. The instrument contains 11 questions based on the ISO 9126-1 model. Out of the six main characteristics identified in ISO 9126-1, only

three characteristics were covered in the instrument: functionality, usability, and efficiency. The choice of the 11 items took into consideration those characteristics that may be clearly experienced by both the personnel in-charge and the students who served as evaluators. The five functionality sub-characteristics included: suitability, accurateness, interoperability, functional compliance, and security. The four usability sub-characteristics included: understandability, learnability, operability, and attractiveness. Finally, two efficiency sub-characteristics included: time behaviour and resourcebehaviour.

Corresponding statement was phrased for each sub-characteristic. Each statement is answerable by strongly disagree, disagree, slightly disagree, slightly agree, agree, and strongly agree with the weight of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 respectively.

Mean was used to determine the overall evaluation and evaluation of the produced software's quality as to functionality, usability, efficiency, and portability. The descriptions of the quality were based on the following scale arbitrarily assigned by the researchers: "very poor" for a mean range of 1.00-2.25, "poor" for a mean range of 2.26-3.50, "good" for a mean range of 3.51-4.75, and "very good" for a mean range of 4.76-6.00.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Software Characteristics

3.1.1. Functionality

On suitability, the software package was developed with two applications—one for the personnel in-charge and the other for the examinees. On accurateness, the setting in terms of the type of exams, number of items, time allocations, choices, correct answers, and passing rates is done by the personnel in-charge. On interoperability, the application for the examinees communicates with the

application of the personnel in-charge. They are sharing similar database. In terms of conformance, the contents authenticated that of the requirements set by the personnel in-charge of the entrance examination. The software provides flexibility in the number of items per set, accommodates either True-False or Multiple Choice item, randomizes questions per examinee, generates statistics of passers and non-passers, and is implemented in local network. In terms of security, separate application is provided for the examinees and personnel in-charge. Username and password are required for the personnel in-charge. Pertinent information is required for each examinee before opening the window for exam questions. System feedback through dialog boxes is included to confirm commands.

3.1.2. Usability

On understandability, related commands are grouped by menu. Command buttons are formatted with the usual format. On learnability, commands are named according to their functions. Corresponding labels for inputs are provided to guide the users of required information. On operability, the software can be operated like any information system. The users have to click the corresponding button or option to invoke a particular command. On attractiveness, the software was built with pertinent font styles, object sizes, and colours.

3.1.3. Efficiency

In terms of time behaviour, it responds almost instantaneously. Completion of certain tasks requires only few clicks. Results of the exam are provided to the examinees immediately after completing the test. The personnel in-charge may view the statistics anytime. On resource behaviour, it consumes a very small amount of memory. To run the software, the recommended specifications are the following: Windows XP, Windows 7, Windows 8, Mac OS 10.8, or Ubuntu for the operating system;

at least 100 MB free disk space; 1GB of RAM, Java Runtime Environment 7; MySQL 5; and at least 1368 x 768 screen resolution. No more paper is required.

3.2 Evaluation of the Software

3.2.1. Personnel In-Charge Evaluation

Table 1 shows the three personnel in-charge's evaluation on the overall quality as well as the quality as to functionality, usability, and efficiency of the software.

Table 1. Evaluation of the Personnel In-Charge

Characteristic	Mean	Description
Overall	4.79	Very good
Functionality	4.80	Very good
Suitability	5.00	Very good
Accurateness	5.00	Very good
Interoperability	4.33	Good
Compliance	5.00	Very good
Security	4.67	Good
Usability	4.92	Very good
Understandability	5.00	Very good
Learnability	5.00	Very good
Operability	4.67	Good
Attractiveness	5.00	Very good
Efficiency	4.67	Good
Time behaviour	5.00	Very good
Resource behaviour	4.33	Good

The evaluation of the three personnel in-charge on the overall quality of the software garnered a "very good" rating.

In terms of functionality, the three personnel in-charge have evaluated the software as "very good". This is constant to its sub-characteristics such as: suitability, accurateness, and compliance. However, its interoperability and security sub-characteristics were evaluated as "good" only.

As to usability, the three personnel in-charge have evaluated the software as "very good". This is consistent to its sub-characteristics such as: understandability, learnability, and attractiveness. Yet, its operability sub-characteristic was evaluated as "good" only.

As to efficiency, the three personnel in-charge have evaluated the software as “good”. This is in conformity to its resource behaviour. But, its time behaviour sub-characteristic was evaluated as “very good”.

Based on the mean evaluation of the three personnel in-charge, the software for the entrance examination possesses a very good quality in terms of functionality and usability. Yet, the software is good as to efficiency.

3.2.2. Students Evaluation

Table 2 shows the evaluation of the students on the overall quality as well as the quality as to functionality, usability, and efficiency of the software.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Students

Characteristic	Mean	Description
Overall	4.42	Good
Functionality	4.27	Good
Suitability	4.37	Good
Accurateness	4.17	Good
Interoperability	4.27	Good
Compliance	4.47	Good
Security	4.10	Good
Usability	4.50	Good
Understandability	4.53	Good
Learnability	4.70	Good
Operability	4.50	Good
Attractiveness	4.27	Good
Efficiency	4.48	Good
Time behaviour	4.37	Good
Resource behaviour	4.60	Good

Students’ evaluation of the overall quality of the software garnered a “good” rating.

As to functionality, the students have evaluated the software as “good”. This is true to all its sub-characteristics such as: suitability, accurateness, interoperability, compliance and security.

As to usability, the students have evaluated the software as “good”. This is consistent to all its sub-characteristics such as: understandability, learnability, operability, and attractiveness. When it comes to efficiency, the students have

evaluated the software as “good”. This is in conformity to its time behaviour and resource behaviour.

Based on the mean evaluation of the students, the developed software for entrance examination possesses a good quality as well as consistent to all its sub-characteristics, namely: functionality, usability, and efficiency.

4. IMPLICATION

The result of this study which produced software package using Java and MySQL implies their capability in providing software that may be used in academic processes. Such programming language and database management system may be effectively used in conjunction with developmental tools like NetBeans and XAMPP. Furthermore, the DFD and ERD are still relevant to model process and data, respectively. Adequate experience of the said tools would provide very good quality software. The results suggest the consideration of those tools in the jobs of information technology professionals specifically in developing information systems.

The developed software has contributed and may continue to contribute in the field of information and communications technology for a more effective and efficient means of completing transactions. Such system minimizes if not totally eliminates the use of papers.

As a result, the evaluation of the students that is lower than the evaluation of the personnel in-charge implies the need to improve the software intended for the examinees. Moreover, other characteristics of the software such as interoperability, security, operability, and resource behaviour intended for the personnel in-charge may still be improved to achieve a very good rating. The developed

software may still be improved taking into consideration the pilot testing results.

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